

ADDRESSING STRUGGLING READERS DIFFERENTIATED NEEDS THROUGH STRUCTURED ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to revolutionize the reading assessment process for struggling readers in accordance with the guidelines set forth by the Department of Education intended for the upcoming National Learning Camp for School Year 2023-2024, whereas DO no. 14 s. 2023 (11.d) principle stated that the NLC shall be guided with purposeful assessment that enhances teaching and learning. The researcher crafted a reading assessment tool that directly determined the specific reading level of the struggling learners. The structured assessment categorized reading levels from A to Z (Fountas & Pinnell, 2017). However, as the study focused solely on the struggling or beginning readers, only Level A-I were emphasized. The researcher employed a Mixed-Method Research Design. The study's participants were ten Key Stage 1 teachers from Antonio Adricula Sr. Memorial Elementary School, located in the Siniloan Sub-Office of Schools Division Office of Laguna. Survey and interview questionnaire were used to gather the data needed in the study. Basic descriptive statistics such as simple mean and the weighted mean were also used to determine the level of acceptability of the developed structured assessment. Based on the findings, all the indicators have a mean ranging from 4.8 to 4.9 and a weighted mean of 4.89. Hence, it was interpreted that the developed structured assessment for addressing the learners differentiated reading needs was Highly Acceptable. Furthermore, it was found out that the challenges in implementation included parental involvement issues and the meagerness of some teachers' aptitude in addressing the complexity of learners' diverse needs.

Keywords: *assessment, reading intervention, elementary, learning camp*

INTRODUCTION

Assessment plays a pivotal role in evaluating reading proficiency and understanding the capabilities of readers. It serves as a fundamental tool in educational settings, aiding educators in tailoring instruction to meet the needs of different learners. The significance of assessment in reading instruction cannot be overstated. It provides valuable insights into learners' strengths, weaknesses and progress over time.

This study aimed to revolutionize the reading assessment process for struggling readers in accordance with the guidelines set forth by the Department of Education intended for the upcoming National Learning Camp for School Year 2023-2024, whereas DO no. 14 s. 2023 (11.d) principle stated that the NLC shall be guided with Purposeful Assessment that Enhances Teaching and Learning, in which it mentioned the significance of assessment as a tool for guiding evidence-based teaching to promote learning. It was also emphasized that learners in the Intervention Camp shall experience support to achieve Foundational Mathematics and or English skills, thus the researcher aimed to create a valid and acceptable assessment focused on aligning, leveling and structuring learners reading levels to accurately identify and address the needs of struggling readers where it aided as an additional basis for assessing the learners' reading capabilities and determining the appropriate learning strategy and materials necessary to them. The structured assessment served as a diagnostic tool, allowing teachers to identify learners' current reading levels and areas requiring improvement.

The researcher's creation of a structured reading assessment tool is paramount, aimed at precisely pinpointing the reading proficiency of struggling learners, particularly those falling within the Frustration Reading level of the Post-test Phil-Iri assessment or identified as Full Refresher or Moderate Refresher in the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA). However, as Valencia & Buly (2004) observed the limitations of standardized test scores in providing a complete picture of struggling readers' needs. They emphasized the importance of using assessment data to inform differentiated instruction and provide targeted support. By discerning the strengths, weaknesses, and specific needs of the learners using the structured assessment, teachers were fully equipped to implement the End-of-School-Year (EOSY) National Learning Camp efficiently. The intervention process involved several key steps:

Assessment Phase. Begun by assessing the learners' current reading levels using the researcher developed structured assessment tool which included the structured standardized test and reading assessment form or inventory. These assessments should cover areas such as decoding, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. The data gathered from assessments provided insights into students' strengths, weaknesses, and areas for growth.

Leveling Phase. Based on the assessment results, determined each student's reading level. Reading levels are typically classified using systems such as Level A, Level B and up to Level I.

Structuring Instruction. Once students' reading levels have been determined, appropriate instruction to provide support and scaffolding were targeted. This may involve grouping students with similar reading levels for targeted instruction, using differentiated instruction to meet individual needs, and providing appropriate scaffolding to support students as they develop their reading skills.

Selecting Materials. Choose reading materials that are appropriate for each student's reading level.

Monitoring Progress. Continuously monitor students' progress as they engage with reading instruction and practice. Use formative assessments, progress monitoring tools, and ongoing observation to track students' growth over time and adjust instruction as needed. Celebrate students' achievements and provide feedback to support their continued development.

Providing Support. Offer targeted support and interventions to students who may be struggling to make progress. This may involve small group instruction, one-on-one support from a reading specialist, or additional resources and accommodations to address specific learning needs.

Reading levels for beginners are categorized based on various systems, but a common one used in education is the Fountas and Pinnell Guided Reading Level (F&P). In this system, reading levels are categorized from A to Z, with Level A being the easiest and Level Z being the most advanced. Here's a general breakdown of how these levels are categorized:

Levels A-C: These levels typically represent the earliest stages of reading development. These levels have simple, repetitive text which often focus on basic sight words and simple vocabulary.

Levels D-I: At these levels, texts become slightly more complex. Sentences may be longer, and there may be more variety in vocabulary and sentence structure.

Levels J-M: These levels indicate a transition to longer texts with more complex plots and characters. Vocabulary becomes more varied, and there may be more dialogue and descriptive language.

Levels N-P: At these levels are considered transitional readers. They contain longer chapters, more complex storylines, and fewer illustrations. Vocabulary is more sophisticated, and readers are expected to use context clues to understand unfamiliar words.

Levels Q-S: At these levels are considered proficient readers. They include longer, more challenging texts with advanced vocabulary and complex themes. These require readers to infer meaning, analyze characters and plot, and make connections between the text and their own experiences.

Levels T-Z: These levels represent advanced readers. Books at these levels are typically full-length novels with sophisticated language and complex themes. Readers are expected to demonstrate deep comprehension, critical thinking skills, and the ability to analyze literature on multiple levels.

These categorizations serve as general guidelines, and individual reading programs may use slightly different criteria for assigning levels (Fountas and Finnell, 2017). Hence, as the researcher aimed to target the struggling or beginning readers and learners who need abrupt attention and immediate actions, the structured assessment focused at Levels A – I exclusively. It must be noted that the study was limited to the said structured assessment levels.

Research Questions

To address the issue of structured assessment in evaluating learners reading capabilities, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants according to age, teaching position, marital status, grade level advisory and years in teaching at the Department of Education?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the developed structured assessment tool in determining the readers' specific reading capabilities and needs?
3. How does the developed structured assessment contribute to identifying specific areas of learners' weakness or learning gaps?
4. What are the benefits and challenges of implementing the developed structured assessment to support struggling readers in diverse classroom settings?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used Mixed-Method Research Design. Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) defined mixed methods research as research in which the investigator collects and analyzes data, integrates the findings, and draws inferences using both qualitative and quantitative approaches or methods in a single study or program of inquiry. Meanwhile, the following framework was used in the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Action Research

The researcher used the Input-Process-Output model or IPO framework to show the clear relationship and process of her research study. Canonizado (2021) emphasized that IPO is the commonly used approach by researchers in various fields and the IPO model represents all the factors that make up the process thus includes all the material and information that are required in the process itself.

The participants of the study were ten (10) Key Stage 1 or KS1 teachers from Antonio Adricula Sr. Memorial Elementary School in Siniloan Sub-Office, Schools Division Office of Laguna. In the study, the researcher politely asked the ten (10) KS1 teachers Antonio Adricula Sr. Memorial Elementary School in Siniloan Sub-Office, Schools Division Office of Laguna to use and implement the structured assessment developed by the researcher to serve as an assessment in determining the learners' specific reading level and identify their weaknesses or learning gaps. The researcher also gave an online questionnaire and interviewed the teachers about the benefits and challenges of conducting the developed structured assessment to support readers in a diverse classroom setting. The structured assessment was also validated at the school level by three authorized teachers from the school resource validation team such as the content validator, language validator and layout and format validator.

To find the answer to the research questions mentioned above, the researcher used basic descriptive statistics such as simple mean and the weighted mean to summarize the five-point scale Likert scale to determine the acceptability scores given by the teachers for each indicator based on the research questionnaire. The researcher also displayed the results using a bar chart to represent the data. All these data were encoded and generated in software such as MS Excel.

In addition, the answers for the qualitative questions which was asked through questionnaire and interview were also discussed using thematic analysis as Caulfield (2019) explained that it was usually applied to a set of text such as an interview or transcripts, closely examines the data to identify common themes.

RESULTS

For the profile of the participants, the ten (10) Key Stage 1 teachers' data such as age, teaching position, marital status, grade level advisory and years in teaching (DepEd) were shown below.

Figure 2. Age of Participants

Based on the graph above, four (4) participants at the age bracket of 41-45 were almost half of the participants population, three (3) were from ages 26-30 and one (1) for each age bracket of 31-35, 36-40 and 60 and above respectively.

Figure 3. Teaching Position of Participants

For the participants' teaching position, four (4) of them belong to the Teacher I position, two (2) Teacher II, three (3) Teacher III and one (1) Master Teacher I.

Figure 4. Marital Status of Participants

With regard to the participants' marital status, the majority of them or eight (8) out of ten participants are married and two (2) are single. It was also found out that there was no widow among the participants.

Figure 5. Grade Level Advisory of Participants

Meanwhile, with regards to their respective grade level advisory, the same number of participants were included to the Kindergarten and Grade 2 level which was two (2) participants for each, and the same also goes to the class of Grade 1 and Grade 3 which was composed of three (3) participants as well.

Figure 6. Years in Teaching (DepEd) of Participants

Lastly on the participants profile, their years in teaching at DepEd also varies, more than half or six (6) of them belong to the 6-10 years in teaching, two (2) at the 11-15 years, and one (1) for 0-5 years and 26-30 years respectively.

For the second research question, which is to determine the level of acceptability of the researcher developed a structured assessment. The participants' answers were summarized in the table below.

Participant/ Indicator	Useful in Determining the (Reading) Strength/ Potential of the Learner	Useful in Determining the (Reading)Weakn ess/ Challenges of the Learner	Readable (size and text appropriate) for the Learner	Suitable to check and record student (reading) performance and output	Reliable to Use as Reading Assessment Tool for key Stage 1 Learners	Helpful for Supporting Struggling Learners	Easy to Use/Administer
Participant 1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Participant 3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 6	5	5	5	4	5	5	5
Participant 7	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 8	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 9	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Participant 10	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Mean	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.8	4.9	4.9	4.9
Weighted Mean	4.89						

Table 1. Level of Acceptability of the Developed Structured Assessment

We can infer from the table above that all the indicators have a mean ranging from 4.8 to 4.9 which can be interpreted as Highly Acceptable based on the Five-Point Likert rating Scale Interpretation, furthermore it can also be supported by its weighted mean of 4.89 which was also further interpreted as Highly Acceptable. Therefore, it can be concluded that the developed structured assessment for addressing the learners differentiated reading needs was Highly Acceptable for the Key Stage 1 teachers view and acknowledgement.

Meanwhile, for the participants response on the research questions, the researcher conducted a survey-interview with the ten (10) Key Stage 1 teachers. Through thematic analysis, their responses at how does the developed structured assessment contribute to identifying learners' weakness or learning gaps. They following themes were discovered:

Determine Learners Weaknesses/Reading Gaps

The findings of the interview revealed that: (a) eight teachers found that the structured assessment can evidently track the learners' weaknesses and learning gaps (reading); (b) some teachers were unable to completely explain how the structured assessment helped them identify the learners weaknesses/learning gaps, but they mentioned that the structured assessment was also helpful to them, such as what mentioned at the second theme below.

Useful in Distinguishing the Learners Reading Level

Participant 4 and 9 particularized that it really helped them distinguished the reading levels of their learners. The remaining participants had similar responses which can be summarized to the usefulness of the structured assessment as it helped them distinguishing their learners' reading levels thus they can strategize or adjust the intervention suited for their learner.

Step-by-Step Process

One particular participant's responses stood out, she answered that as it (structured assessment) was a step-by-step process, she can easily follow the procedure in administering the reading assessment, thus realize the weaknesses of learners.

Based on the participants' responses, it was apparent that the structured assessment was a comprehensive tool that aided in identifying learners' weaknesses and learning gaps. It supported teachers by recognizing the specific reading levels of their learners and its step-by-step process which helped them realize appropriate intervention or support needed to address the differentiated needs of learners.

For the last research question which is about the benefits and challenges in implementing structured assessment to support struggling readers, the responses of the participants were as follows:

Determine the Learners' Specific Reading Level

Based on the participants responses, Participant 1, 4 and 9 highlighted the benefit of using the structured assessment as it served as a guide for teachers to determine the specific reading level of the learners. It helped them realize where they would begin or what appropriate intervention should they provide to their specific learner.

Assess Learners Strengths and Weaknesses

The structured assessment allowed the identification of not just the learners weaknesses or learning needs but also the learners' strength (reading). As Participant 6 and 10 pointed out, the structured assessment also provided opportunities for the learners to showcase their improvement and reading progress. Consequently, if the learners were still found out to be in the lower reading level, the structured assessment could still aid the teacher in developing their individualized support plans, as mentioned by Participant 8.

Lack of Parents Cooperation/Communication

Meanwhile, four participants heavily emphasized the challenges they encountered when administering the structured assessment. They elaborated that as they inform the parents of the struggling readers to the conduct of the project/structured assessment, the politely requested their learners to participate or be present during the day of their assessment, however a lot of them failed to do so, therefore they have to administer it again to those said learners, in which it affected some of the lessons or class schedule of the whole class.

Teachers Aptitude and Time Constraint

A couple of participants alluded that after administering the structured assessment to the struggling readers, a hint of worry was realized due to the challenge of creating the individualized support plan for their learners. They added that assessing each student's specific need can be time-consuming.

In conclusion, as the structured assessment offered significant benefits for teachers and learners such as guiding instruction, identifying needs, providing targeted interventions and supporting learner development. It also presented challenges which includes parental involvement issues and the struggle of some teachers in addressing the complexity of learners' diverse needs through structured process.

DISCUSSION

After the implementation of the study, surely it reveals several key insights, the study made emphasis on the importance of tailoring educational strategies to accommodate the diverse abilities and learning style present in any classroom. By employing structured assessment, teachers can systematically identify individual strengths and areas for improvement, enabling more personalized instruction. Structured assessments provide a clear framework for evaluating reading skill or level of the learner, making it easier to pinpoint specific needs such as phonemic awareness, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension. This targeted approach ensures that interventions are precise and effective, enhancing the likelihood of academic success for the Key Stage 1 learners.

Moreover, the study also highlighted the role of continuous assessment in monitoring progress and adapting teaching methods. As Tomlinson (2001) emphasized the importance of ongoing assessment to tailor instruction to individual student needs and discusses various methods of formative and summative assessment to guide instructional decisions. In essence, the study underscores the critical role of structured assessment in creating an inclusive and responsive educational environment. By recognizing and addressing the varied needs of learners, teachers can foster a more equitable and effective reading instruction framework ultimately leading to improved literacy outcomes.

Moreover, it was recommended that further collaborative planning and providing necessary training and materials to teachers would greatly benefit the learners as the teachers would be highly equipped with knowledge and skills to cater to the complexity of handling diverse struggling readers. The comprehensive understanding of benefits and challenges can help teachers refine and improve the implementation of structured assessment to support struggling readers effectively. One study pointed out that many teachers feel unprepared to effectively support students from diverse background due to lack of proper training and resources. This lack of preparation can lead to feelings of inadequacy and reluctance to address students' needs in the classroom (ACEE, 2023).

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions were drawn for each research questions:

1. The developed structured assessment was found to be highly acceptable from the perspective of the Key Stage 1 teachers. The mean scores ranged from 4.8 – 4.9 on Five-Point Likert rating scale, with a weighted mean of 4.89, all interpreted as “Highly Acceptable”. This demonstrated a strong endorsement of the assessment’s design and utility by the teachers.

2. The structured assessment was effective in identifying specific areas of learners’ weaknesses or learning gaps. Participants reported that it provided feedback on students’ performance, highlighting both strengths and areas needing improvement. This feedback was crucial in understanding learners’ specific needs. The step-by-step level of the assessment helped teachers determine the reading levels and create interventions accordingly, confirming its usefulness in pinpointing and addressing learning gaps.

3. The structured assessment offered several benefits. It guided teachers in addressing the needs of struggling readers by identifying specific learning gaps through a detailed and structured process. Teachers found it highly useful in planning targeted instruction. However, the implementation faced challenges, particularly the lack of cooperation and communication from parents, which hindered the effectiveness of the approach. This highlights the need for strategies to improve parental involvement to fully realize the benefits of the assessment-driven approach.

In conclusion, the structured assessment is highly acceptable to Key Stage 1 teachers, effectively identifies learners’ reading needs, and offers significant instructional benefits though it faces challenges in parental engagement and teachers’ aptitude.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings and conclusions, here are several recommendations:

1. To address the challenge of lack of parental cooperation and communication, school should implement strategies to increase parental involvement. This could include regular parent-teacher meetings, workshops for parents on supporting reading at home and clear communication channels between teachers and parents.

2. Provide continuous professional development opportunities for teachers to effectively use the structured assessment tool. Training should focus on interpreting

assessment results, designing targeted interventions, and utilizing feedback to support differentiated instructions.

3. Foster a collaborative approach among teachers, reading specialists and administrators to support the implementation of the assessment-driven approach. Sharing best practices and successful strategies can enhance the overall effectiveness. Further studies which extends to the limitations of the study was also recommended.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a declaration by the author in her own word and in paragraph form which includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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